

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

A STUDY OF SOME SOFTWARE TOOLS USED IN TRANSPORT ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to show the advantages of the application of various types of software packages and tools in the planning, management, control, forecasting of traffic in cities and non-urban environments and of course in projecting. Streets are a traditional platform for the movement of vehicles, so they should be well designed, arranged to have a greater appeal to pedestrians, cyclists and offer sufficient security and safety for them. One of the modern Streetscape software tools is used to display a cross section of a particular street with the elements we want to place.

Keywords: Software tools, design, re/design, elements, street.

Introduction

The increasing influence of information technologies, the evolution of software engineering, and the development of intelligent transportation systems have enabled traffic simulation to become a leading approach for traffic analysis and for supporting the operation and setting of traffic systems. Simulation models are effective tools that enable assessment of various traffic situations. They are of enormous help for analyzing the existing situation, for evaluating the problems that arise and for proposing more effective solutions.

The traffic simulation supports transportation planning and traffic management. New solutions and measures can be effectively tested in a "virtual reality" environment, without disrupting traffic on the ground. Effective traffic management and control strategy is the result of verified (verified) and evaluated (validated) output indicators of efficiency from the simulation. In recent years, traffic simulation, ie microscopic traffic simulation, has moved from the academic to the professional world.

There is a large supply of traffic simulation software, as well as its application by researchers, design companies, and engineers in the field of traffic. Urban design is related to town planning, but focuses on the physical design of public space and details.

Types of Software Tools and Packages

Software tools and packages facilitate the work of traffic engineers by offering them opportunities for virtual creation of various scenarios, their simulation, development of variant solutions and analysis of the existing conditions in the functioning of traffic and transport, especially in cities. The software tools are applied in the following areas: road engineering and management, safety and accident analysis, traffic planning, public transport planning, street infrastructure design, and so on. The term simulation is defined as a dynamic representation of a part of the real world achieved by building a computer model and moving it over time.

Computer models are widely used in the analysis of traffic and transportation system.

Traffic models and simulation tools are increasingly used to manage traffic on wide area road networks using real-time data. These systems were developed for traffic modeling, planning and comparing different traffic control strategies in real time.

Traffic modeling and simulations have an irreplaceable place in the planning of transport infrastructure. The design of road networks and intersections, analysis of traffic situations to eliminate congestion, reduce vehicle delays and improve road safety are the subject of much research work. Most of them are based on creating and analyzing microscopic models.

There are a number of software packages for the analysis of isolated junctions and signal plans: HCS – capacity and level of service analysis software, SIDRA – signalized junctions which serves to determine the operation of signals, phases, number and length of lanes, software for analysis in relation to roundabouts, intersections controlled by a STOP sign – HCS(TWSC/AWSC), VISSIM – software for determining how the intersection works and with simulation it is possible to see how vehicles move, what problems arise and their solution without going out on the field. VISUM planning and forecasting transport demand, modeling all road users, by neighborhoods in urban areas, cities, regions and entire countries.

Software for operational analysis of intersections, streets, thoroughfares, network, software for operational analysis of non-urban roads and ramps for vehicles. With the help of these softwares it is possible to determine the capacity of the road, the level of service, speed, travel time, costs, congestion, fuel consumption, emissions, etc. DataFromSky Viewer is a professional desktop application that is used to analyze the movement of objects within the video. DataFromSky service detects objects, their movements, interactions and based on this information, you can work with data, information and statistics on the raw video data.

Fig. 1. A window from the Data From Sky software

Fig. 2. A window and simulation from the VISSIM software

Fig. 3. A window from the VISUM software

The Streetscape Software Tool

Streetscape Pro is a tool for the conceptual design of urban streets. You can enter parameters such as: the width of the lanes and sidewalks, the height of the surrounding buildings, after which the cross section of the street design will be automatically set. Images can be used for attachment in reports or presentations, and designs can be imported into CityCAD and applied to a 3D model.

The design creates functional, active and scenic streets that provide opportunities for walking, cycling, transit use, recreational use and social interaction. The successful coordination of these elements makes it possible to create a surface accessible to everyone. Streetscape creates attractive and safe streets, which are

the foundation for the future development of communities.

A sustainable streetscape plays an important role in forming the visual image of sustainable cities, as it is one of the most important factors that contribute to the success of a city and a tourist attraction. However, there are many cities whose visual image lacks the presence of an accurate and sustainable street character, which negatively affects the visual image of these cities, and consequently the place of those cities at the global level. By applying a sustainable streetscape that encompasses architectural, environmental, social and economic aspects, it can help to achieve sustainable urban design, and thus a sustainable city.[1]

Fig. 4. A window from the Streetscape software

Tool features

With the help of this tool, the street design can be created with any of the elements – sidewalks, vehicle lanes, bus lanes, bicycles, footpaths, greenery, can be arranged in any order from left to right. The height of the buildings on both sides can also be adjusted, it can be determined how much the street will be shaded at different times of the year. Counting parking spaces can be tedious. You can add parking elements to your street design (parallel, 30, 45, 60, or 90 degrees) and this tool will automatically estimate the total number of spaces for a given length of street. This tool can also be used to display the overall street height to width ratio.

Objectives of the sustainable streetscape

Streetscape must create a good environment for people. Social and economic interactions are the main goals of good street design.

- Improving the quality of the environment by "improving air quality, improving water quality".
- "Maintaining economic vitality by reducing the consumption of material resources."
- Maintaining limited natural resources at the regional level by reducing energy use, water use and stormwater runoff by increasing porous surface and landscaping.
- Maintaining the urban fabric by improving the visual image of the city,

- Contributing to improving public health by encouraging walking and other recreational activities within the community.

Street design elements

Streets make up more than 80% of public space in cities, but they often fail to provide surrounding communities with a space where people can safely walk, bike, drive, transit and socialize. Cities are leading the movement to redesign and reinvest our streets as cherished public spaces for people as well as critical arteries for traffic. The Street Guide to Urban Design outlines the principles and practices of the nation's foremost engineers, planners, and designers working in cities today.

- Sidewalks

Sidewalks play a vital role in city life. As channels for pedestrian movement and access, they improve connectivity and promote walking. As public spaces, sidewalks serve as front steps to the city, activating streets socially and economically. Safe, accessible, well-maintained, well-designed and green sidewalks, with a sufficient amount of urban equipment, bench placement are a basic and necessary investment for cities. Sidewalks should be designed so that they can serve a larger number of pedestrians and provide enough space to expand to the roadway and place other types of urban equipment or furniture, such as trash receptacles, bus stops, signaling and bike sharing stations and fig.[2]

Fig. 5. Urban design of pavements using software tools

- Greenery

Planting greenery adds color, texture, and interest to a space and helps define, separate, and enhance aesthetic value. Saplings planted on paths should not create congestion or block pedestrian areas, and placement

on street corners should not obstruct the driver's view. They can be placed in seating areas, along the edges of parking lots, in pedestrian squares. Planting plants and trees leads to greening and better design of the space, reduction of noise, better air, etc.

Fig. 6. Placement of greenery with the help of the tool until implementation on the ground

- Street equipment

It should be consistent and coordinated in design, materials, colors and styles that will complement the architectural style. Placement and design elements should be coordinated to avoid visual clutter. These elements may include lighting fixtures, waste receptacles, benches. Benches are important public resources that help make a city a pleasant place for pedestrians. It is preferable to make them from sustainable or recycled

materials in order to achieve economic efficiency and a sustainable street look. Lighting is an important element in the streetscape, it should contribute to the creation of a safe and aesthetically pleasing public space. Garbage receptacles can be one of the most used elements of the street and should be conveniently located on pedestrian zones, near benches, bus stops and other nodes of activity.[3]

Fig. 7. Placement of street equipment, benches, trash cans, lighting

- Bicycle lane

As a result of the increased degree of motorization, air pollution, congestion, noise, lately the use of alternative modes of transportation is increasing, therefore it is of great importance to have well designed and built bicycle paths, lanes and equipment. The bicycle as a means has a number of advantages, in addition to the environment and human health. In order to use it more,

people need to feel safe, we need to have a lane along the entire length, if the bike lanes are together with the rest of the traffic, they should be marked along the length with color, separation with a protective fence, or the best way is to be away from the rest of the motorized traffic (protected area). The path consists of colored asphalt, a smooth surface for cycling.

Fig. 8. Bicycle lane arrangement

- Motor Vehicles Lane

Cars have many conveniences in terms of privacy, convenience, comfort, but they are still one of the biggest polluters of the environment. With the process of motorization, there was a need for a redesign of the

street infrastructure, so pedestrian paths were taken over with lanes for motor vehicles. The strips can be imposed only for cars or for trucks, they can also be used by public vehicles. [4]

Fig. 9. Motor vehicles lane

- Bus lanes

Public transport has experienced a resurgence in the last few years, following investments in rail, buses, bus priority measures, a new bus network. A properly functioning public transport system is a key component of successful, accessible cities. Public transport services and design can significantly contribute to improving the quality of life for residents and a better urban environment. A medium-sized bus takes up the space

of three cars, but can carry 50 people. This efficiency helps ensure that urban areas are vibrant, allowing large numbers of people to arrive while not using up a lot of space. Public transport facilities should be carefully designed to integrate and support other street functions. Designs must take into account pedestrian volumes, the nature and vision of the street, passenger use and the volume of public transport vehicles.[5]

Fig. 10. The lane for buses in relation to passenger vehicles

- Parking

A parking area is a place where a vehicle rests. Although it sounds paradoxical, one of the key conditions that affects the quality of traffic in the city is actually the organization of idle traffic, i.e. vehicle parking. In doing so, we are primarily referring to the parking of individual passenger vehicles, which, due to their number, are the cause of the burden on the traffic network and the congestion of the city intersections, and also create the need for huge areas for parking in the

entire territory of the city. The magnitude of the problem of parking individual passenger vehicles can be understood if we know that on average even 90% of the time during the day, passenger vehicles spend it at rest. Therefore, the provision of adequate parking space is extremely important for the smooth functioning of the traffic system in the city. Parking can be on or off-street. Depending on the parking angle, we have at an angle of 30, 45, 60, 90 longitudinally, that is, along the edge of the roadway.

Fig. 11. Lane for parking in a traffic flow zone

Introduction to the software tool

Streetscape pro 2.0.1 Streetscape Pro is a quick and easy tool for creating scale and cross-section plans of various street designs. By changing the design in the input panel on the left, we can see in the center what the drawing will look like. If you make any changes to the data, such as widths, on the left, then the display is immediately updated on the right.

→ Main parts of the software tool The four main parts of Streetscape Pro are:

1. Input panel that includes: General data, street attachment, street elements and note entry. These three groups can be collected by clicking on the arrow at the top right of each of them.
2. The screen window, which displays scaled-down 2D drawings of your street design.
3. Street analysis panel that shows information about your street design.
4. Urban design database panel where you can search for real-world streets with the same width as your current image.[1]

Fig. 12. Streetscape Pro 2.0.1 software tool overview

Initial steps associated with the software tool

When you first open Streetscape Pro, a sample street is open. Each Streetscape Pro file is composed of Streetscape Elements such as vehicle lanes, pavements or reservations. These are listed in the "Streetscape Elements" list in the input panel on the left. Elements can be created, edited and deleted using the buttons at the

top of this list. The order in which they appear on the street (from left to right) can also be changed. You can modify the traffic lane width by clicking. A standard starting street consists of four Streetscape Elements - a sidewalk, two vehicle lanes, and a second sidewalk. These are listed in the input panel on the left.[1]

Fig. 13. Opening a new document and a window that appears

Adding a street element

Click on add vehicle lane. Then click the little arrow next to the plus sign above, and choose "Add Booking". You'll see a reservation being inserted into the center of the road.[6]

Fig.14. Adding a street element

The addition of trees
 First it is necessary to adjust the width of the Reservation to about 2 m to allow space for the trees. Then in the Streetscape Elements bar, click the small plus

sign next to the Reservation item to display the data being entered. In the "Trees" row, click the word "Disabled" to bring up the menu and select "Enabled".[7]

Fig.15. Addition of trees

Installation of parking strip
 By clicking on the first sidewalk in the Streetscape Elements List. Then add a parking lane using the down arrow opens what lane we want, we select a parking lane. Parking should appear in the main screen window. Next, if you click on the little plus sign to the left of the

Parking name, it should expand to show you the detailed options. Next to "Configuration", try selecting "45-degree", then press back. In the main display window, this should be updated to show parallel parking.[8]

Fig.16. Installation of parallel parking strip

Adding information about the costs of your street
 Using the same street model as before, try clicking on the little plus sign next to "Price" in the "Parking"

element. The line should be expanded to show construction costs and maintenance costs. As an example, write a price of £200/m.

Fig.17. Adding information about the costs of your street

Use street analysis information
 Parking and cost information can now be analyzed in the street analysis panel. In order for Streetscape Pro

to calculate the total values, you need to enter a length for the street. Enter a length of 100 meters in the upper left corner of the Street Analysis Panel.

Fig.18. Use street analysis information

Name and street orientation can be entered. in the street annex, the characteristics of the buildings on both sides of the street can be edited. You can adjust the building's height and depth by entering the measurements here. You can enter the number of entrances on each side of the street, you can also choose a color for

the window shading. This tool allows animation of vehicle movements.

Displaying the Window

The display window is where the street design visualization is shown. There are five main sections: Title, Section, Handle, Plan, Scale bar.

Fig.19. Show the displaying the window

Database of urban design

Any time you are creating a street design, you can select the button "Find real-world streets of similar width". This will search our database of real-world

streets that you can use as references for your current street design. When the results are displayed, you can select one and it will open with more details in a new browser window.

Fig.20. Database of urban design

We can also choose a currency, usually it is Euro, shadow and sun. It is also possible to choose from which side we want the vehicles to be driven, whether from the left or right depending on the Earth. You can

manually enter the sun's azimuth (direction) and sun's height (angle from the horizon), enter them in the field, or use the sliders.[9]

Fig.21. Placement in sun and shade, driving side

Examples with the application of the software tool

Fig.22. Created examples with the software tool Streetscape pro 2.0.1

Conclusion

Today, the use and availability of a large number of software tools is of great importance to traffic engineers. There are several software packages and tools that are used to plan, analyze, project the traffic routes. With them, it is much easier, without going out into the field with data entry, to determine all future errors and to solve them before starting the application of the project. In this article, an example is the software tool Streetscape pro 2.0.1 which allows to design the street appearance, how the traffic roads will look like and animation of the work done. Streets are the traditional way in which traffic flows. On the streets we have the movement of pedestrians, cyclists, cars, buses, good design of pedestrian and bicycle lanes is of great importance in order to attract the alternative mode of transportation and avoid individual vehicles. As part of the examples section, is given a presentation and analysis of several roads and determined that by applying the street design, the functioning of the traffic flows, and thus the traffic congestion and the modal distribution of the flows, can be greatly influenced. This directly affects the pollution, the noise and the quality of life in cities.

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